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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“MY MOTHER...”

My mother loved, sacrificed, and endured a lot for me to reach my goals. Despite the adversities in life, she never hesitated to support me, especially in my studies. I am overwhelmed with grief gazing at what remained. I miss the times when you ramble, reminisce about the past challenges we went through, and smile at the achievements I have.

My mother is one of the models of pure strength that a child needs and motivation for every child who dreams. She worked hard as a utility worker in our barangay, “namunlay,” and “nangutang”—she did whatever it took to earn so we could finish our studies. She never showed us that she is already tired of finding ways to support our dreams but always shows her joy and hope that one day I will be able to graduate. I am just so grateful for her.

Through the support she and Papa gave, I was able to finish my studies and was able to have a stable job. But it's heartbreaking to recall that there were times when I did not understand her. There were times I felt distant from her. But now that she's gone, I understand that she did all that for my own good.

I may not be able to show and express to her how much I care and love her; I know in my heart that I am very proud of having a mother like her. I will not be able to become who I am right now without her believing and trusting me. Her love, support and prayers pushed me to strive hard and achieve not just my goals but hers as well.

Now that she's gone, I can't stop my tears from falling because of deep longing to spend more time with her. I can't see her anymore; I can't have a funny and deep conversation with her anymore. It's so heartbreaking. But despite all, I am still happy and thankful to God giving me a caring, loving and supportive mother for more than 37 years. I will always cherish her sacrifices.

Mama, salamat sa tanan. Gihigugma tika ug mingawon gyud ko nimo pirme.